

A New Photoactivated Fluorescence Detection Method for Trichloroethylene

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We describe here a novel method using photoactivated fluorescence for the detection of trichloroethylene (TCE). The approach involves photoactivation by uv irradiation of TCE in the presence of a photoactivator, diphenylamine, subsequent excitation of the photoproduct complex, and detection of the luminescent photoproduct. The photoproduct exhibits new absorption fluorescent bands. Conventional fixed-wavelength excitation and synchronous luminescence (SL) are used for detection.

Trichloroethylene (TCE) is considered as an important environmental health hazard because high concentrations of TCE induce tumor growth in mice¹. TCE pollution is a global environmental problem because this compound has been widely used in the past as a common industrial solvent². TCE has been identified as the most common contaminant found at 546 Superfund sites³. In addition, many sites of the U.S. Department of Energy are contaminated with mixtures of volatile organochloride compounds (VOCs) including TCE. Since TCE is soluble and mobile in ground water and soil⁴, its rapid identification and containment are imperative. Most of the analytical techniques used for TCE and VOCs generally employ a chromatographic separation coupled to a specific detection scheme (e.g. flame ionization, electron capture, photoionization etc.). Using the Fujirama's reaction⁵, a colorimetric sensor has been developed, which takes advantage of the intense red color developed by pyridine⁶. Recently, a luminescence spot test has also been developed for other chlorinated species such as the polychlorinated biphenyls⁷.

We describe here a new method using photoactivated fluorescence for the detection of trichloroethylene. Fluorescence is well known for its sensitivity and selectivity. This technique, however, is not applicable to weakly fluorescent or non-fluorescent compounds such as TCE. An indirect method is required to produce a fluorescent product. The principle of detection involves a photochemical reaction that produces a fluorescent product. The experimental procedures (Fig. 1) involve the following steps : (A) a sample holder (capillary quartz tube) containing a solution of a photo-activator (diphenylamine) is exposed to TCE; (B) photoactivation of the mixture is performed by uv irradiation using a portable lamp at 254 nm; (C) the photoproduct complex is subsequently excited (355–360 nm), and the fluorescence of the product is detected using conventional fixed-wavelength excitation or synchronous luminescence (SL) for improved selectivity.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the photoactivated fluorescence method for TCE detection.

Results and Discussion

In the presence of a suitable photo-activator (Ph) illumination of TCE with uv light results in the formation of a luminescent photoproduct (photoactivator-TCE complex). In order to demonstrate the feasibility of the photoactivation approach for TCE detection, we performed experiments using probes consisting of capillary quartz tubes containing approximately 90 μ l of an ethanolic solution of DPA. We have investigated the optimal concentration of the DPA solution from 10^{-4} to 10^{-1} M and found that the DPA

concentration of 10^{-2} M provides the maximum photoproduct signal under the experimental conditions investigated for TCE concentration ranges (10^{-6} – 10^{-3} M). The analyte was introduced into the probe adding different amounts of ethanolic solution of TCE into the probe. Following uv irradiation (254 nm) of the mixture of TCE and DPA with a hand-held lamp, the photocomplex PhC is formed. When subjected to excitation at approximately 360 nm, this photocomplex PhC exhibits a broad-band luminescence emission at 400–520 nm (Fig. 2A, solid curve). The fluorescence of the TCE photocomplex with a broad maximum band at 470 nm is very different from that of photoactivated DPA alone (Fig. 2B, solid curve) which has a fluorescence maximum at 365 nm. The excitation spectrum (which is equivalent to an absorption spectrum) of the TCE-DPA photoproduct (shown in Fig. 2A, dashed curve) exhibits three new bands at approximately 260, 360 and 400 nm, which are different from the main fluorescence excitation band of DPA at approximately 300 nm (Fig. 2B, dashed curve). These results indicate that the TCE photoproduct can be detected by either fluorescence spectrometry (due to the new fluorescence emission band at 470 nm) or by absorption (or colorimetric) techniques (due to the new absorption bands at 260, 360 and 400 nm, with broad bands extending to 440 nm). Appearance of these new absorp-

tion bands could be related to our observation of a light brownish-yellow colored product formed in the sample following photoactivation. Although these results indicated that absorption and colorimetric methods could also be used to detect the TCE-DPA photoproduct, this study deals mainly with the fluorescence method. This work is also focussed on the fluorescence technique because of the inherently superior sensitivity of emission techniques over absorption or colorimetric techniques.

A series of measurements were performed to investigate the kinetics of production of the luminescent photoproduct. The results showed that formation of the product increases with time as indicated by the increase in luminescence intensity. The fluorescence intensity reached a maximum within 10–20 min. The following reaction mechanisms many be involved :

(a) Formation of photoproduct (PhC) :

(b) Excitation of photoproduct :

(c) Luminescence detection of photoproduct :

where, $h\nu_1$ is the use irradiation for photoactivation, $h\nu_2$ the excitation of the photocomplex PhC, $h\nu_3$ the luminescence from the excited state of the photocomplex (PhC)*, Ph the photo-activator (e.g. DPA), PhC the ground-state of the photocomplex (photo-activator + TCE) following $h\nu_1$ irradiation, and PhC* the excited electronic state of PhC.

Experiments using various excitation wavelengths were performed to investigate the spectral characteristics of the photoproduct. The 325 nm excitation was used first to induce fluorescence of DPA and the photoproduct. With a sample containing only DPA, a strong emission peak at 365 nm associated with DPA fluorescence band was observed. When TCE was added to DPA, and the resulting mixture subjected to 254 nm irradiation, the luminescence peak of DPA at 365 nm decreased, whereas a new luminescence emission band (400–520 nm) having a peak at approximately 470 nm appeared. The 400–520 nm luminescence band was associated with the TCE-DPA photocomplex since it did not occur with TCE or DPA alone, and its intensity was proportional to the amount of TCE added to the DPA sample. When we used a longer-wavelength excitation at 390 nm (instead of 325 nm), the photoproduct fluorescence band was observed with much less interference from the 365 nm band of DPA. This improvement in detection was due to the fact that DPA is not excited by the

Fig. 2. Luminescence spectra of (a) excitation (em. wavelength at 460 nm) and emission (exc. wavelength at 355 nm) spectrum of TCE-DPA complex, and (b) excitation (em. wavelength at 380 nm) and emission (exc. wavelength at 300 nm) spectra of DPA.

390 nm excitation light, and thus did not interfere with the measurement.

The selectivity of the detection method was greatly improved by using the synchronous excitation or synchronous luminescence (SL) method. The synchronous methodology consists of scanning both excitation and emission wavelengths simultaneously, by keeping a constant wavelength interval between them⁸. The SL procedure reduces the emission spectrum of individual analyte into a narrow band, therefore decreasing spectral overlap and enhancing the selectivity of the analysis^{8,9}.

Fig. 3 shows the SL spectrum of TCE-DPA photoproduct using a wavelength interval of 10 nm. The SL technique narrows the emission bands of the photoproduct, and produces a well resolved SL peak at about 410 nm (emission wavelength scale = excitation wavelength + 10 nm), thus permitting a better spectral separation of the TCE photoproducts in complex mixtures. Whereas the fixed-excitation fluorescence spectrum of TCE-DPA product (compare with Fig. 2, curve A) exhibits a broad band of approximately 100 nm, the SF peak has a bandwidth of only 10 nm. It is noteworthy that the SL spectrum in Fig. 3 shows two bands at 400 and 440 nm, thus indicating the possibility of formation of two photoproducts.

Fig. 3. Synchronous luminescence spectrum of TCE-DPA photoproduct.

Fig. 4 illustrates the possibility for quantitative analysis by showing the fluorescence intensity (emission at 400 nm; excitation at 360 nm) as a function of TCE concentrations in various water samples spiked with different amount

Fig. 4. Quantitative calibration curve for TCE.

of TCE. The relative standard deviation for quantitative analysis is approximately 10% using multiple replicate measurements. This reproducibility is very good, considering the various experimental steps (viz. sample delivery, photoactivation, excitation, and detection) involved in the procedure. The results demonstrate that quantification is possible for TCE. The LOD value, calculated as the lowest amount of analyte producing a signal equal to 3 times the background noise of the blank sample (i.e. photoactivated DPA alone), is 1 ppm using a commercial Perkin-Elmer instrument. To illustrate its usefulness, we employed the photoactivated luminescence method to screen TCE in several real-life and synthetic samples. Wastewater samples of the Oak Ridge Y-12 plant, a river sample and a tap water spiked with known amount of TCE were used. The analysis showed that TCE in the Y-12 and river samples were below the detection limit (<1 ppm), whereas the spiked samples contained TCE as expected.

An obvious advantage of the technique, besides its simplicity, is the small amounts of sample (microliter volume in a capillary tube) and reagent that are required for each measurement, whereas solution fluorimetry generally requires 1–4 ml. Therefore the absolute limit of optical detection (LOD) is very low, in the sub-nanogram range. The use of small sample volumes will also allow the possibility for developing miniaturized probes that can be incorporated onto the tips of fiberoptic sensors for remote and *in situ* monitoring of TCE. This possibility is currently under investigation in our laboratory.

Spectral interferences from other important chlorinated species such as PCBs have also been evaluated. First, it is important that there is sufficient amount of the photoactivator DPA in order to induce the necessary reaction. This condition is generally satisfied by the relatively concentrated solution of the DPA reagent used (10^{-2} M). The results indicated that PCBs do not interfere with the analysis of TCE because the TCE photoproduct is completely dif-

ferent in emission and excitation from that with PCB photoproducts when used with DPA. The PCB photoproduct with DPA must be excited at wavelength <360 nm (e.g. 325 nm, whereas the TCE photoproduct with DPA exhibits absorption up to 450 nm (see excitation spectrum in Fig. 1, curve B).

Conclusion : Due to the environmental significance of TCE, there is a need to develop alternative methods and chemical sensors to detect TCE and VOCs under field conditions. This study demonstrates that the photoactivation method using fluorescence detection can be used to screen for TCE. The screening method is particularly attractive for TCE on a routine basis. The technique is simple and uses inexpensive reagents, materials and small amount of samples ($1 \mu\text{l}$). Due to its simplicity and fast response, the technique has a great potential for rapid screening of TCE under field conditions, and for decreasing the cost of TCE remediation.

Experimental

All fluorescence measurements were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 650-40 spectrofluorimeter equipped with a 150 W xenon lamp and a Hamamatsu photomultiplier (R928). A hand-held ultraviolet lamp (UVGL-58, UVP Products) was used as the uv source for photoactivation. The sample holders consisted of quartz capillary tubes (2 mm i.d., 8 mm o.d., 2 cm length) inserted in the sample compartment of the spectrofluorimeter.

Spectroscopic-grade TCE (Aldrich) was used as received. Diphenylamine (Eastman Kodak) and undenatured 200-proof ethanol (Warner Graham Co.) were used.

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